

Infrastructure Futures for Digital Cultural Heritage

Jen Ross, Philippa Sheail, Melissa
Terras and Cate Schofield

University of Edinburgh

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Executive Summary

This report presents the findings of a study focused on infrastructure futures for digital cultural heritage, considering the processes and practices of preserving, managing, sharing and maintaining the cultural legacy of groups and societies in digital formats. We recognise digital cultural heritage as encompassing both digitised and born-digital artifacts and their tangible and intangible attributes, for preservation, management, research, and educational use. This necessitates dedicated infrastructures to support the complexities of digital preservation, access, analysis, and dissemination of heritage. The project explored the infrastructural needs and challenges associated with digital cultural heritage, aiming to understand current priorities, concerns, and hopes by imagining future possibilities through speculative design. A set of future scenarios were developed through a literature review and expert interviews, to provoke thought and discussion among stakeholders. These scenarios were explored through a survey and workshops, which allowed for the collection of diverse perspectives on digital cultural heritage infrastructures.

The project identified several persistent issues in digital cultural heritage, including sustainability challenges due to short-term funding, difficulties in sharing knowledge across diverse disciplinary and operational contexts, and the impact of power dynamics on the inclusivity and accessibility of infrastructures. Additionally, the speculative scenarios highlighted that there is no one-size-fits-all solution to infrastructure design, emphasising the need for flexible, adaptable approaches that consider the varied needs of Gallery, Library, Archive, and Museum (GLAM) institutions and the communities they serve.

Based on project discussions and feedback from participants involved in the study, we recommend:

1. Increasing sustainable funding and support for long-term infrastructure projects to stabilise digital cultural heritage infrastructure efforts and support stakeholders' ability to imagine and enact positive futures.
2. Recognising the increasing importance of specialist, expert voices in navigating the complex terrain of digital infrastructures, and ensuring experts have the stability, space and time to engage in strategic planning, work collaboratively and share their expertise.
3. Defining sustainability expansively and accounting for sustainable environmental, labour and collaboration practices and policies at all stages of infrastructure work.
4. Undertaking more work to understand and communicate the different values informing digital cultural heritage and its infrastructures, in order to decide where best to deploy existing resources and lobby for further support. For example, there is a critical balance to be struck between standardising for interoperability and encouraging innovation through open-source platforms and community-driven development.

This research was undertaken at the University of Edinburgh in 2023/4, with small project funding from the Creative Informatics, the Edinburgh-based AHRC Creative Industries Cluster.

By using speculative design as a research framework, the project engaged stakeholders in critical discussions about the potential and pitfalls of various infrastructural models. This approach enriched the dialogue around digital cultural heritage infrastructures, and demonstrated the usefulness of creative, forward-thinking methodologies in addressing complex issues in their planning and development. The research highlighted that while digital transformation offers tremendous possibilities for accessing and preserving cultural heritage, it also requires careful consideration of infrastructural support to realise these benefits sustainably. The insights garnered from this project are expected to inform future decisions on funding, policy-making, and strategic planning, and to serve as a model of speculative design for institutions to adopt when exploring innovative solutions to emerging challenges in digital infrastructure.

Introduction

Digital cultural heritage - the processes and practices of preserving, managing, sharing and maintaining an inherited legacy of tangible physical and digital artifacts and attributes of groups and societies using digital formats - has arisen from society's digital turn, but requires its own digital infrastructures. What do we mean when we talk about infrastructure for digital cultural heritage research? How can we get a better understanding of current priorities, concerns and hopes by imagining and collectively scrutinising possibilities for the future? These two questions informed this research project at the University of Edinburgh, UK, funded by the [Creative Informatics AHRC Creative Industries Cluster](#). It aimed to surface the decisions that professionals in the Gallery, Library, Archive, and Museum sector – and related stewards of culture such as universities and community groups – have made, and continue to make, when developing and using digital infrastructures for cultural heritage, and the ongoing implications of these decisions.

To explore our research questions, we developed a set of speculative scenarios, distilled and imagined from the results of a literature review and 9 expert interviews undertaken in late 2023 and early 2024. The scenarios formed the basis of a survey (127 responses) and two workshops held in April 2024 (with a total of 32 participants), which sought engagement with the scenarios and the futures they suggested.

In common with the way infrastructure is defined (or not), and the different levels at which it is understood to operate (or not), including at the human, technological, institutional or policy level, these speculative scenarios were built on a range of ideas about what the future might look like, and what Gallery, Library, Archive and Museum (GLAM) digital infrastructures are for, with different underpinning assumptions explored. The scenarios were not intended to be correct or ideal solutions: our aim was to provoke discussion that built in a fresh way on ongoing conversations regarding audience, resourcing, governance, and stages of technological development. The timing of this project coincided with the aftermath of the high-profile and highly destructive cyber-attack on the [British Library in 2023](#), meaning that a number of issues around digital infrastructure became even more urgent topics of discussion in digital humanities and digital cultural heritage organisations and networks in the UK (where a large number of our respondents and participants were based), as well as internationally.

In addition to analysing participant responses to the different scenarios, this report draws out a number of key findings around leadership, organisational forms, resourcing, sustainability, data, and different kinds of relationships on which future infrastructure might depend. Rather than attempting to draw specific conclusions about what the future of infrastructure should or will look like, we highlight the values, tensions, possibilities and constraints that are shaping attitudes to the future in this domain, and explore what kind of foundation these create for innovative and sustainable forms of digital cultural heritage infrastructure.

Reviewing Infrastructure: Definitions, Key Challenges, and Future Visions

Our scenarios and interview questions were informed by a wide-ranging review of relevant literature, drawing out key themes relating to issues of infrastructure and infrastructure futures. Our reading on digital infrastructure included scholarly and industry publications from a range of disciplines and locations. This reflects the many contexts and disciplines which engage in conceptual work on infrastructure, as well as those which relate directly to digital cultural heritage infrastructures.

Defining Infrastructure

When introducing digital infrastructure during the project, we used Mark Parsons' broad definition: 'the relationships, interactions and connections between people, technologies, and institutions (that help data flow and be useful)' (2015), which draws attention to several key features.

Firstly, it makes clear that infrastructure is a way to connect, network, manage or link otherwise independent things together (Blanke et al., 2017; Borgman, 2007; Edwards et al., 2013; Goodrich et al., 2022; Plantin et al., 2018). Some scholars therefore see infrastructure as a technical system, linking information and information technologies (Ahnert et al., 2023; Budka, 2015; Hughes, 2014; Richardson, 2022; Sendra et al., 2023).

However, a fuller definition of infrastructure encompasses that system plus people: Liu (2018) describes this as a ‘social-cum-technological milieu’ (p2). This definition suggests that infrastructure is instantiated and realised through its use and users (Bowker et al., 2010; Cardwell et al., 2022; Champion, 2012; Edwards et al., 2013; Hughes et al., 2017; Koch, 2017; Pawlicka-Deger, 2022). It acknowledges that infrastructural connections can also be interpersonal, and power dynamics affect connection and therefore inclusion (Capurro et al., 2023; Marttila and Botero, 2021). Furthermore, whilst people shape infrastructure, infrastructure also shapes how people know and act, with societal ramifications (Datta, 2023; Gran et al., 2019; Koch, 2017; Liu, 2018; Plets et al., 2023; Viola, 2023). Some scholars even suggest that digital infrastructure can ‘create new realities’ (Plets et al., 2023; see also Capurro et al., 2023).

Key Issues and Challenges in Digital Infrastructure

A major digital infrastructure challenge is sustainability. Short-term funding leads to short-term projects, with limited longevity (Edmond and Morselli, 2020; Fensham et al., 2024; Hughes, 2014; Woodley and Towell, 2022). This impacts individual infrastructures, but also knowledge, as opportunities to build on or share learning is limited: there is a lack of discussion, reflection, acknowledgement and trust around digital infrastructures, despite social relations being so key (Ahnert et al., 2023; Borgman, 2007; Capurro et al., 2023; Champion, 2012; RICHES Project, 2016; Hughes et al., 2017; Marttila and Botero, 2021; Rutherford, 2023). Another issue with knowledge sharing is digital infrastructure’s many contexts, which splits scholarship between different disciplinary norms and terminologies (Clutterbuck, 2022; Sendra et al., 2023), and means participating scholars often lack the digital training necessary to know what is possible (Jaillant and Aske, 2024; Jensen, 2021). This means infrastructure often builds from pre-digital conceptions of heritage infrastructure, which replicate hierarchical and colonial patterns of access, often falling back on print models (Capurro et al., 2023; Crane, 2023; Goodrich et al., 2022; Gran et al., 2019; Mauro-Flude, 2019; Rutherford, 2023; Soergel, 2002; Woodley and Towell, 2022). This ignores the potential of digital infrastructure, and its larger scales of data and access (Bowker et al., 2010; Edmond and Morselli, 2020; Jensen, 2021). As a result, discussions about what scales infrastructures should serve (Gran et al., 2019; Koch, 2017; Pyo and Gu, 2023), and make for sustainable projects (Borgman, 2007; Edwards et al., 2013; Lenstra, 2017), remain unresolved, as knowledge, funds and access (Pawlicka-Deger, 2022) remain unevenly distributed.

Power and knowledge are also major issues for digital infrastructure. No matter how infrastructure is organised and operated, certain narratives will be included and others lost (Budka, 2015; Mauro-Flude, 2019; Plantin et al., 2018; Plets et al., 2023). Different models of infrastructure come with their own issues: commercial infrastructure is shaped by corporate interests (Anderson and Blanke, 2012; Edwards et al., 2013; Plantin et al., 2018); institutional infrastructure risks perpetuating exclusionary, extractive or historic practices (Almas, 2017; Crane, 2023; Gran et al., 2019; Hansson, 2023; Rutherford, 2023); government-run infrastructure depends on political agendas (Datta, 2023); and open infrastructure faces security and licencing issues (Ahnert et al., 2023; Crane, 2023). In each, however, an infrastructure’s creation of knowledge and power actually depends on the technical experts and institutions who created it, despite technology’s perceived neutrality (Lenstra, 2017; Plets et al., 2023; Viola, 2023). An infrastructure implicitly presents its knowledge as objective truth, whilst other forms ‘may be lost or rendered unthinkable’ (Edwards et al., 2013). Tacit (Borgman, 2007; Edwards et al., 2013), disciplinary (Mauro-Flude, 2019), human-scale (Anderson and Blanke, 2012) and uncertain knowledge (Middle et al., 2023) become necessary to protect.

Infrastructure Futures

By critiquing digital infrastructure, scholars make implicit and deliberate claims about what can or should be (made) possible in the future. Some scholars foresee a shift to privatisation (Gran et al., 2019; Plantin et al., 2018), to make up for an unsustainable funding situation in the present. Others imagine community-run projects, maintained through participation and sharing (Budka, 2015; Edwards et al., 2013; Hughes et al., 2017). These are made viable because of the international networking capabilities of digital technology (Blanke et al., 2017; Mauro-Flude, 2019). In these futures, users are central to infrastructure, running it and therefore challenging the power hierarchies of top-down models. Less radically, some scholars advocate for user-centric infrastructures which emphasise considering, connecting and trusting all possible users, but do not depend on their labour, having a more formal or centralised structure with consistent staffing (Champion, 2012; Edmond et al., 2017; Rutherford, 2023; Sendra et al., 2023).

Much literature advocates for infrastructure built on open data, to counteract siloing which separates present infrastructures from each other (Champion, 2012; Crane, 2023; European Policy Brief, 2016; Hughes, 2014; Marttila and Botero, 2021). More data would become available, and new forms of scholarship, sustainability, searching and methods could utilise digital tools to provide new ways to access this (Edmond and Morselli, 2020; Edwards et al., 2013; Jaillant and Aske, 2024; Soergel, 2002). However, openness has limitations: Steyn and Goodrich advocate for ‘delinking’ to ‘disrupt the production of European body political and geopolitical knowledge, as universal’ (2022). There is no single objective or ethical answer, then. Some scholars suggest that infrastructure must be value-driven, employing staff and systems which challenge and work against negative norms, by being equitable and representative (Pawlicka-Deger, 2022; Rutherford, 2023), feminist (Mauro-Flude, 2019; Sutherland et al., 2023) or queer (Hansson, 2023). Such a shift in infrastructure values could create a new reality for heritage work, methods and knowledge.

Summary of Context: Digital Cultural Heritage Infrastructures

We define cultural heritage as the legacy of tangible physical artifacts and intangible attributes of groups and societies that are inherited from past generations, maintained in the present, and bestowed for the benefit of future generations. Cultural heritage has its own presence, requirements, procedures, and practices that stem from the digital turn. “Digital cultural heritage” refers to the process and practice of preserving and managing cultural heritage in digital formats. This encompasses efforts to digitise historical artifacts, artworks, monuments, documents, audio, and films, ensuring these cultural assets are preserved, archived, and made accessible using digital technologies. The concept extends beyond preservation to include the reinterpretation and reuse of cultural content in ways that may not be possible with their physical counterparts, and also increasingly includes the capture and preservation of born-digital cultural heritage. As such, digital cultural heritage is a large area that encompasses digitisation, digital preservation, access and dissemination, interactivity and engagement, and related legal and ethical aspects, as well as considering different motivations, users and use cases, including research, education, and the preservation of at-risk cultures. There are a variety of tasks associated with digital cultural heritage, including high-quality digitisation, metadata creation, data storage and digital preservation, access control and security, data integration and interoperability, sustainability planning, user interface and experience design, legal and ethical management, quality assurance, and disaster recovery and risk-management. For more insight into digital cultural heritage contexts, practices and infrastructures over the past two decades, see Hughes (2004), MacDonald (2006), Cameron and Kenderdine (2007), Kalay, Kvan and Affleck (2008), Coutts (2016), Kidd (2016), Corrado and Sandy (2017), and Bernardou, Champion, Dallas and Hughes (2018).

A range of platforms deliver cultural heritage, including: [British Library Images Online](#), [Canadiana](#), [Digital Public Library of America \(DPLA\)](#), [Europeana](#), [Flickr Commons](#), [Google Arts & Culture](#), [Internet Archive](#), [Project Gutenberg](#), [The Library of Congress Digital Collections](#), [Trove](#),

[UNESCO's World Digital Library](#) and [Wikimedia](#). It is tempting to think of these type of platforms as the infrastructures that underpin the management and use of digital cultural heritage, but as well as these user- and audience-facing databases of content, there is a range of commercial and open-source tools which support the development, management, and preservation of collections (some of which are designed specifically for the GLAM sector, some of which have wider application but are utilised by GLAMs).

For example, there are Digital Asset Management Systems like [ResourceSpace](#), and [Goobi](#); Preservation and Archiving Software such as [Archivematica](#) and [Preservica](#); Collection Management Systems including [CollectiveAccess](#), [PastPerfect](#), and [TMS \(The Museum System\)](#); Digital Repository Services like [Islandora](#), [DSpace](#), [Digital Commons](#), [CONTENTdm](#), and [Omeka](#); Visualization and Mapping Tools such as [R](#), [Gephi](#), and [StoryMap JS](#); 3D Imaging and Virtual Reality software including [Agisoft Metashape](#), [Autodesk ReCap](#), [Unity](#), and [Unreal Engine](#); Advanced Text Recognition tools such as [ABBYY FineReader](#), and [Transkribus](#); Text Analysis Tools including [Voyant Tools](#), [Gale Digital Scholar Lab](#), and [Python NLTK](#); and Interoperability and Data Exchange Standards such as [Dublin Core](#), [CIDOC CRM](#), and [IIIF \(International Image Interoperability Framework\)](#).

In the UK, there are also centrally funded data repositories to steward particular types of datasets, such as the [Archaeology Data Service](#), and the AHRC funded [Research Infrastructure for Conservation and Heritage Science \(RICHeS\) programme for Heritage Science data](#). At time of the writing (summer 2024), the AHRC's [Towards a National Collection](#) large-scale funded programme is preparing its final recommendations on “research that breaks down the barriers that exist between the UK's outstanding cultural heritage collections, with the aim of opening them up to new research opportunities and encouraging the public to explore them in new ways”. The European Union provides support for a number of infrastructural initiatives in this space including:

- the [Ariadne Research Infrastructure](#), which promotes, supports and develops the use of digital techniques applied to the arts, humanities, cultural heritage and, in particular, to archaeology;
- [DARIAH-EU](#), a research infrastructure that enhances and supports digitally enabled research and teaching across the Arts and Humanities;
- [CLARIN](#), the research infrastructure for language as social and cultural data;
- the new [Cultural Heritage Cloud](#), which aims to harmonise and interconnect cultural heritage institutions and research organisations, removing barriers for smaller and remote institutions.

The infrastructural space in digital cultural heritage is multi-faceted, overlapping, international, unevenly distributed, and exhibits numerous biases. It is supported by a diverse range of providers including government-funded entities, commercial companies, not-for-profit organisations, and open-source contributors, along with volunteers who develop tools, platforms, systems, and repositories, and researchers who aim to co-design, critique, and document developments.

As a result, the field of digital cultural heritage produces, manages and stewards a vast volume of disparate data, and its data management needs are both complex and crucial, ensuring that digital assets are not only preserved accurately and securely but are also accessible and usable for future generations. Saving, securing, delivering, and allowing access to digital cultural heritage thus requires a variety of digital infrastructures, and a variety of choices to be made about resourcing and supporting those infrastructures that reflect and develop best and current practice.

The main actors in this space (predominantly GLAM institutions and universities, but also amateur collectors, schools, churches, and community groups, and so on) are expected to keep up to date with technological developments and evolving user needs, although they usually operate without the resources or people-power of major technology providers: “in the aftermath of the financial and debt crisis, European governments have approved austerity policies which have brutally affected culture and the arts” (Cirillo and De Tullio, 2021, p.5). The cultural heritage sector therefore needs to balance a variety of needs, values, requirements, and resourcing constraints regarding digital cultural heritage infrastructure: this necessitates making difficult choices about potential options for digital futures in this unique space. What these choices, and futures, could look like, and what responses different futures generate, were the focus of this project.

Methodology

A Speculative Approach

Speculative research methods are increasingly being used to explore digital futures in a range of sectors, including education and heritage (Ross 2023). Speculative approaches are methods that “work with the future as a space of uncertainty, and use that uncertainty creatively in the present” (Ross 2023). Rather than being predictive, speculative methods such as scenario building can aim for representation and understanding of multiple futures (Staley 2007), and what these might have to tell us about the past and present (Milojevic 2005). The aim of using speculative methods in this project was to achieve what Dunne and Raby (2013) describe as “loosen[ing], even just a bit, reality’s grip on our imagination” (p.3).

To do this, we aimed to stimulate fresh discussions on a broad topic which we recognised may have become stale (in the context of multiple approaches and limited funding), but also critical (in the light of a major cyber-attack on the British Library) to future challenges and developments. Our hope was that developing partial future narratives around key themes, drawing on expertise, and with a sense of being respectfully playful with key issues, might be a point of departure for new conversations. In our expert interview schedules, for example, we included a question asking what participants were ‘tired of talking about’ in relation to infrastructure.

We wrote our scenarios in the form of partial stories from the future, which we used to frame organisational and technical issues and practices in the field, highlighting positive and negative implications, rather than specific organisations and technologies. These were developed as provocations for interesting discussions, underpinned by questions and challenges that our participants were likely to be familiar with, but also able to contribute to in a focused way. We also intended for these illustrated scenarios to be freely available for analysis and strategic planning within other organisations and teams, so they also exist as standalone artefacts to be used and reused in different contexts. For this reason, we made them openly available via our [project web page](#).

We took a phased approach to generating our research data, drawing initially on a review of the literature and early discussions to inform the development of semi-structured interview questions. A set of expert interviews then formed the basis of work to develop eight speculative future scenarios, drawing on our developing understanding of the current ‘state of play’ of digital cultural heritage infrastructure and the key challenges and opportunities identified.

This phased development resulted in multiple – predominantly qualitative – data sources, and involved development of speculative scenarios and illustrations that were worked on in an iterative way by the team. This approach was therefore more resource-intensive than some other forms of survey preparation and workshop facilitation. However, we felt this made particularly good use of expertise in the field, starting with recognised issues and sketching partial answers – with many intentional gaps – intended as provocations.

Ethical approval for this project was granted by the University of Edinburgh's Moray House School of Education and Sport Research Ethics Committee.

We welcomed and were able to engage with the broad range of experience and expertise brought to the project by our participants and their interpretations of the research materials.

It is also worth highlighting that one of the successes of this project was our collective ability to draw on an established professional network and prior work. We recognise the irony of how this project reflects some of the positive and negative aspects of our own Buddy System scenario, including its dependency on academic social capital, and on the Old Farm scenario discussed later in this report.

Expert Interviews

We began our work with research participants by identifying a group of potential interviewees with expertise in digital cultural heritage and the digital humanities. Initial participants were identified by the research team, and interviewees also made recommendations for subsequent participants. Our invitations were facilitated by the involvement of Professor Terras as a respected and high-profile researcher in the field. We undertook nine expert interviews, each conducted by a member of the research team. These were held online using Microsoft Teams and were scheduled for 45 minutes. Recorded audio files were transcribed by an external third-party, and we checked them for accuracy during our analysis. We sought permission from each of our experts to list their names in our research outputs and on our project website.

Scenario Development

All nine interview transcripts were read and annotated by the whole team, independently and then in an analysis meeting where common themes and departures were identified which could contribute to the development of the scenarios. Themes were considered in relation to the literature review, our own professional experience, and with a focus on how they would serve the goal of scenario building. Eight scenarios were drafted, further discussed, and the texts finalised. We then worked with a graphic designer, who developed scenario illustrations to help evoke the key ideas in each. The completed scenarios were published online, incorporated into a survey, and formed the foundation for workshop discussions.

Survey Design

Survey participants were asked four initial questions about their location, professional context and level of expertise with digital cultural heritage infrastructure. We then developed eight questions – a combination of multiple choice and free text responses – to be answered about one or more individual scenarios.

These questions included judgements about how desirable and achievable each scenario was, as well as the following free text questions:

- Does this scenario describe an organisation or way of working that already exists in the current international landscape? Can you tell us more?
- How would you describe this way of working?
- What is most interesting or problematic in this scenario?
- Does this scenario prompt any thoughts about current digital cultural heritage infrastructure you are familiar with? How?

Respondents were then invited to give any further comments about the specific scenario, and to respond to a further scenario if they wished – this cycle could be repeated multiple times until all scenarios had been seen. Finally, respondents were asked if they had any comments about the survey or the approach.

The survey was designed in the online survey platform [Qualtrics](#), and a key feature of this design was to present each participant with a random scenario for comment, giving the option to respond to as many or as few additional scenarios as their time and interest allowed. The survey was distributed via professional email lists and social media, particularly targeting respondents researching or studying in the digital humanities, with digital cultural heritage, and/or working in professional roles in the GLAM sector.

The survey was open between 3–30 April 2024. In total we received 127 responses to the survey.

More survey respondents described themselves as “somewhat knowledgeable” about digital infrastructure (39%) than experts (16%) or very knowledgeable (30%), but combined, most participants had existing knowledge to draw on. A few had little knowledge (8%), with just over 1% saying they had no knowledge (but were curious). This is important context for the responses below – as we would expect, most of those who took the time to access and complete the survey were familiar with concepts around digital infrastructure.

Figure 1: Respondent level of familiarity with digital infrastructure.

For the nearly half of respondents who were very knowledgeable or experts in this area, we can also assume existing perspectives on the debates and issues expressed through the scenarios, and this assumption was borne out by the thoughtful and knowledgeable responses given.

This knowledge was often associated with respondents' roles in universities or in the GLAM sector: 61 respondents (48%) worked in Higher Education, with 37 (29%) working in galleries, libraries, archives or museums. Other organisational contexts included digital humanities centres (8%), government (7%), commercial organisations of various sizes (9%). One respondent was working in a funding organisation, 11 (8%) worked in other contexts, and 9 (7%) had no affiliation. A number of people selected more than one option, indicating roles in multiple kinds of organisations.

Figure 2: Types of organisations worked in by respondents.

Almost half of respondents (42%) were located in the UK, with the rest coming from countries in Europe (24%), from North and South America (10%), and from Australia (3 people), with 1 respondent each from Israel, South Africa, and Vietnam. A number of people did not specify their location (20%), but we can conclude that the survey responses, like the workshop responses, are significantly informed by developments and cultural heritage structures in the UK and Europe.

Figure 3: Locations of respondents by country.

Research Workshops

Once the survey was published, two workshops were advertised, again via professional email networks, with registration available via Eventbrite. The first workshop was held in-person on 18 April 2024 at [St Cecilia's Hall](#), Edinburgh (11 participants), and the second workshop was held online on 24 April 2024 via Zoom (21 participants). Both events were facilitated by the research team and each workshop lasted for two hours.

In preparation for the in-person event, poster versions of each scenario text were set out around the workshop venue, so that discussion groups were able to self-select and gather around a chosen title. Post-it notes were provided so that comments could be added directly to the posters. We also distributed A4 scenario print-outs for quick reference, and printed stickers of the scenario illustrations which were later used by participant discussion groups for voting and as take-aways from the session.

At the beginning of the workshop, we presented an overview of the project, some brief background on the literature and methodology, and summaries of the scenarios to the group. Members of the research team were available to facilitate and engage with scenario discussions. We also took photographs of posters and notes, and took our own notes of the wider group discussion, for later analysis.

The online workshop followed a similar format and began with the same introductory presentations. Attendees were then randomly allocated to discussion groups by an administrator, and selected the scenarios they wished to discuss, with a research team member contributing to each group and making notes. Groups were also given a link to a shared document for notetaking.

In total, there were 32 participants across the two workshops. The in-person and online workshop encouraged slightly different demographics, although both were more weighted towards the higher education sector than other organisation types, compared with the survey. Across both workshops, participants represented both digital cultural heritage users and creators. Most workshop participants (68%) worked at higher education institutions. In fact, during the in-person workshop, which was hosted at the University of Edinburgh, this rose to 90%. The rest of the participants were part of the GLAM sector, coming particularly from libraries and museums. However, their organisations varied significantly in type and size, ranging from community heritage organisations to national libraries. It is worth noting that although many participants came from universities, they were not all academics. Some participants did research work in museums, or library work from within universities, and just under 20% had a job related to digital services. Academics themselves were at various career stages, so that we heard from PhD students alongside senior lecturers.

Participants were largely associated with organisations based in the UK, and spoke from and about the UK context. Almost 90% of institutions it was possible to identify a location for were based in either Scotland (52%) or England (36%). Unsurprisingly, most of the Scotland-based participants attended the in-person workshop in Edinburgh. Most of the participants for the online workshop were based in England, with a number of international participants also in attendance online.

Data Analysis

Data generated in the project consisted of 9 interview transcripts; 127 survey responses; and 2 sets of workshop notes. The transcripts formed the basis of development and writing activities for scenario building. We looked in particular for similarities to, and departures from, our reading and early discussions. A more detailed analysis of the expert interviews will be included in a forthcoming publication. Survey responses were exported to Excel. Qualitative responses to each scenario were coded and summarised for each scenario prompt. We met again to discuss our summaries and to draw out themes, again referring back to our reading of the literature and to our previous discussions of the expert interviews. Our analysis and findings are discussed below.

Insights from Expert Interviews

Key insights we drew on to inform the scenarios ranged considerably across a spectrum of digital infrastructure dimensions, including technical, political, social and economic. This reflects our invitation to interviewees to consider infrastructure from whichever perspectives were most relevant to them, and we began each interview by sharing our own working definition: “relationships, interactions and connections between people, technologies, and institutions (that help data flow and be useful)” (Parsons 2015) to underscore this. As a result of the range of interviewees and their areas of interest, discussions about infrastructure engaged with a number of ideas, including:

Balancing change and stability – the perceived need for novelty, innovation and imagination in developing infrastructure and attracting investment towards organisations and the sector was weighed against core requirements for stability, reliability and foundational services that can enable access and allow innovation to flourish and (importantly) be shared. Some of these foundational services are mundane and open-ended, such as the ongoing process of cataloguing. And some forms of change are not truly innovative, or are hampered by short-term understandings of what is required or what the future may bring (generative AI was mentioned in this context, for example). In developing our scenarios, we explored futures where stability is the highest priority (creating issues for the development of new ideas); and those which suggest a more ad hoc and emergent way of working.

Degrees of centralisation – the relative advantages of centralisation and distribution of ownership and care of collections and infrastructure came up often. A vision of reliable, generic and standardised structures that could be built on to create bespoke and novel applications and approaches was put forward, as was the notion of caring for large or at-risk collections by distributing ownership and care. A number of scenarios explored different aspects of distribution.

Collaboration and competition – risks and disadvantages that come with a competitive cultural heritage and infrastructure landscape were identified: driving activity in specific, limited directions and reducing diversity; and foregrounding financial value and extractive practices. However, competition was also understood as having potential to spark innovation and to generate positive new ways of working. Collaboration was seen as complex both to foster and to sustain, but essential to create both formal and informal connections that underpin a successful shared infrastructure. Aspects of these discussions are reflected in various scenarios.

Other important issues raised in the interviews included:

- **Skills and capacities** – what these are, how they develop and are shared, and where they are located within and between organisations. Understanding skills and capacities as, in themselves, infrastructures, informed our scenario-building.
- **Funding and resources** – scenarios highlight different models for considering funding and sustainability of digital infrastructures, which was one of the key tensions that emerged in interviews.

- **Technological change** – our scenarios explore different infrastructure technology futures – AI-driven, socially networked, or minimally resource-intensive – all of which came up in the interviews in discussion of what sorts of technologies and digital practices might inform future infrastructure.
- **Knowledge systems and gaps** – one of the most frequently raised issues in the interviews was about the different ways that knowledge of the past and ideas of the present are encoded in infrastructure decisions, and what is left out. This included discussion of how to include and preserve context alongside digital objects. It also reflects ambitions around data management practice in the sector, for example [FAIR \(Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable\)](#) principles.
- **Politics of infrastructure** – the extent to which infrastructure decisions can and should be driven from the top-down (from governments, funders, large institutions, consortia) or from the bottom up (in polyvocal, institutional or user-driven ways, for example) was discussed at length in the interviews. The political nature of infrastructure itself was part of this discussion, as was the wider political climate in which the sector is operating. Most of the scenarios reflect this issue in some way, presenting different political structures within which digital infrastructure might operate.
- **Long-term thinking and preservation** – for a variety of reasons, the issue of preservation and thinking for the long term was important in these interviews. Preservation discussion included digital objects and collections, but also what one person referred to as the “spirit” of their organisation, and the nature of impact and value of digital cultural heritage. The relationship of preservation and access, and the need for collaboration to enable rapid responses to emergent issues, are reflected in a number of scenarios.

What we heard in these interviews confirmed that digital cultural heritage infrastructure futures need to be examined from multiple perspectives. The scenarios are therefore not intended as straightforward objects to compare, but as prompts and provocations to explore a wide range of intersecting, divergent or even conflicting values and possibilities.

The Scenarios

The eight scenarios produced for the project are ordered here according to what survey and workshop participants identified as most to least likely as futures for digital cultural heritage infrastructure. This ordering is not intended to prioritise the familiar or feasible, but to show something about the moment in which these scenarios were produced.

Each scenario is presented and discussed individually in this section, with findings and discussion about emerging themes in the following section. The comments incorporate responses from both the survey and the workshops.

A PDF version of the full scenarios can be downloaded from the project website: <https://www.de.ed.ac.uk/project/infrastructure-futures-digital-cultural-heritage>

We welcome the re-use of these resources as digital infrastructure discussion prompts.

Old Farm

On the Old Farm, cultural heritage infrastructure is siloed. Institutions individually control the digital management and sharing of their collections, using whichever tools suit their needs. Overseeing these activities is a digital regulatory body, which mandates a certain level of quality of public resource. The regulator's standards must be met for institutions to be certified. To ensure the infrastructure is maintained after being put in place, inspections are carried out on a regular basis. In return, the regulator offers several benefits. Getting certification gives institutions access to ringfenced funds. The regulator's technical staff provide skills training, which is particularly useful for smaller institutions who might lack the resources to employ a technician. Its close involvement with institutions helps the body identify and connect different silos who might learn from each other. Finally, certification means promotion on the regulating body's website, which contains a list of properly managed infrastructure institutions. This list is also an indispensable resource for researchers seeking quality digital resources which are specialised according to the institutions and experts managing them.

Survey responses to the Old Farm were broadly positive – over three quarters of survey respondents thought it was desirable. Workshop participants found it more problematic, but across both, respondents felt it was likely to be achievable. In fact, many people across the survey and the workshop felt the Old Farm already existed, at least in parts, and were reminded of a variety of different infrastructures and organisations (including their own). Its siloed nature was recognised as typical of the current cultural heritage sector, and some people thought its certification role was also already being carried out (although others disagreed).

This familiarity was greeted with frustration, but it was acknowledged to be a practical option, which would work with systems which already exist. Although these existing models make the Old Farm more likely, several respondents were hesitant or negative about the infrastructure it reminded them of, observing that good intentions do not always work out in practice. Moreover, some felt that examples of Old Farm approaches were already old-fashioned. As efforts are made to unsilo/desilo heritage institutions, the Old Farm represents the infrastructure status quo that people are trying to challenge, rather than a viable future vision.

Respondents thought that maintaining silos would keep institutions isolated, keep researchers from finding resources, and keep new connections and knowledge from being generated, siloing attitudes and cultures as well as data. One survey respondent suggested that keeping information siloed might affect cultural heritage's accessibility to AI-driven infrastructure in the future. Others suggested that the centralised managing body risked being conservative, self-interested, or trying an inappropriate one-size-fits-all approach, limiting experimentation.

Respondents also pointed out that the diversity of heritage institutions meant that standards and support would be difficult to manage because the technical knowledge and practice ranges so widely. There was, however, a positive response to the idea of offering certification, and particularly technical support.

There was a sense that, if done well, the Old Farm was a pragmatic compromise between having centralised standards, and allowing institutions to maintain their independence, expertise and specialisations.

Related to this, there was also a defence of silos from a handful of respondents, in the context of the value of protecting Indigenous and other marginalised peoples and collections from the gaze and intervention of European and settler colonial institutions. In general, when siloing was positively framed, it was related to independence, or protection of data and knowledge.

National Treasures

Cultural heritage collections are the new Olympics. Government funding is secured in a number of countries to create portals that carefully control messages regarding a nation's collections, broadcasting each country's heritage and accomplishments to the world. It is a political priority to actively influence worldwide online discussion, and money is consistently made available for digitisation, delivery, and promotion of selected national treasures. Content is allowed if it meets strict criteria, sticking to established narratives, and rejecting discussions of alternative histories or expanded representation. Access is free, in a push-only service. Open licensing allows branded resources to be reused in a wide variety of platforms and content. There is fierce competition between nations to rule the Wi-Fi-waves.

National Treasures was received more negatively than most of the other scenarios, with only 4 of the 23 survey responses to this scenario calling it desirable, and workshop participants identifying it as one of the most problematic scenarios. It was, however, seen as possible – 19 survey respondents thought it probably or definitely was feasible.

Several quite different national contexts and initiatives were mentioned as having some resonance with this approach. However, the strongest connections were less to present-day contexts and more to the perceived ambition of organisations and governments to use cultural heritage in the service of political aims. Many respondents framed this in terms of propaganda, authoritarianism and fascism, but others saw it more pragmatically as an extension of 'soft power' initiatives and attempts to meet consumer demands ("giving people what they want").

The question of "who decides?" was at the forefront of many survey and workshop responses to this scenario. Attempts to control narratives or ban diversity were recognised as underpinning ideas here, but so too was the nature of incentives in contexts as diverse as research (where funders can dictate agendas), heritage management (where the temptation of resources might override ethical dilemmas), and government (whose job it is to shape particular outcomes).

Above all, this way of working was seen as inherently vulnerable to political systems and to actors with goals that are incompatible with the belief, expressed by many respondents, that history is a “shared practice”, that established narratives change, that its infrastructure should be able to adapt in times of change, that learning through heritage requires honest reckoning with conflicts and difference, and that collections and stories should be globally connected, not nationally protected.

The potential challenges in such a future could be to the democratisation of archives and history, the existence of local, alternative and non-official heritage, and the ability to foreground nuance and opposing views.

Respondents expressed concern that this scenario, though undesirable, could become inevitable in the face of resource constraints. However, the idea that government would value heritage enough support it financially in this way, even with strings attached, was suggested to be unrealistic.

Pay to Play

Digital collections of culture are a lazy asset that require an infrastructure to sweat them. Borrowing a Software as a Service (SaaS) business model, the full infrastructure can be used only by paying subscribers. A range of membership tiers gives differing access to collections, storage facilities, and analysis tools. Collections are added to the infrastructure based on who can pay for digitisation and ingest. Membership fees are expected to cover infrastructure costs including development and future upkeep. A freemium model ensures entry level access (low resolution images, restricted access to analytics, no storage) for individuals and institutions unwilling or unable to pay. There are also extremely limited numbers of small grants for digitisation of diverse collections, and some central resources for systematic cataloguing to agreed standards. These measures offset criticism about elitism and selling old wine in new bottles. This is market-driven cultural heritage at its digital capitalist best.

This scenario was met with a decided lack of enthusiasm, but also with a sense of resignation, captured by this comment:

“It’s not the best of all possible worlds, but it’s something at least. Otherwise we can keep on waiting another few decades for that huge digitisation investment to come with no strings attached.”

Most survey respondents (15 of 19) found it probably not or definitely not desirable, but the same proportion (16 of 19) thought it was probably or definitely achievable. Additionally, in-person workshop participants thought it was both the most probable and most problematic scenario in equal measure, with online participants discussing it as a future they do not want to live in, but which could easily be entered into.

The reason for this is that “Pay to Play” addresses one of the most significant issues facing the sector – resourcing – but at a very high cost to values and practices of openness. Indeed, many respondents saw an explicit trade-off here – money for values. During the workshops, it was explicitly contrasted with values of openness and access which were positioned as fundamental to cultural heritage work. Respondents saw ethical risks, for example in allowing extractive businesses to become aggressive stakeholders in preserving, studying, and disseminating cultural heritage, in shutting out community and institutional participation, and in commodification of metadata and reduction of access.

However, more optimistic takes on the relationship between this model and values expressed by respondents included the potential this held to “treat digital cultural heritage as content that deserves a proper digital infrastructure”, to make higher quality digitised materials available freely (after a period of charging, for example), to create a more sustainable model for protecting cultural heritage data, to value digital cultural heritage as much as material heritage, and for developing new and better approaches to curation and marketing of digital cultural heritage. Indeed, one respondent thought the scenario itself presented an overly negative picture of what such a model could look like, pointing to co-operatives as an example of a structure that is not profit-driven, but could operate an infrastructure like this.

This point was illustrated in an intriguing way by the large number of examples given by respondents of organisations that had some similarities to this model: [ARIADNE Research Infrastructure](#); [Bloomsbury Fashion Central](#); [Gale’s Digital Scholar Lab](#); [Wikimedia](#); [Europeana](#); [Museum Data Service by the Collections Trust](#); JISC’s [Archives and Libraries Hubs](#); and a former collaboration between [Wellcome and Digirati on the Digital Library Cloud Service](#). Beyond these, examples of streaming platforms for films and music; and several pointed comparisons with academic publishing, were shared by respondents.

One complexity this exposes is the question of who is paying. A number of survey respondents assumed it would be the end users of the collections who would pay, while others recognised the scenario’s intention to illustrate a structure where cultural heritage organisations paid. However, several respondents pointed to the porous boundary between providers and users of cultural heritage data, and others pointed out that in any case, only the largest and wealthiest organisations could really benefit from the access such a model would enable. The question of who pays was a key one, however, with it being agreed that someone has to – but, in the existing political landscape, that it wouldn’t be publicly funded via governments.

Buddy System

Shared infrastructure consists of a basic backbone of communications and data sharing. [D(DIY) CH] is a social network site for accessing Digital Cultural Heritage and Digital Humanities expertise in a peer-to-peer format, where members highlight areas of expertise and showcase projects in progress. The site is populated by professionals and researchers at all career stages. Most non-communications infrastructure and tools are seen as fragile and temporary. Major investments in such projects are rare and they are generally not designed to last. Instead, the emphasis is increasingly on mobilising projects, people and resources for emergent needs. Bespoke tools and approaches are made to fit the problem at hand, and to be quickly adapted or repurposed. Some needs, such as major emergencies and crises, are big enough to draw people together, but most successes rely on having the social capital to interest experts and peers in particular projects. Tools, ideas and projects proliferate and then vanish, often without enough traces left behind to allow them to be recovered or adapted if they become relevant again. However, the communication mechanisms are robust, and you can always ask the network.

Some characterised this scenario as most like academic or Digital Humanities Twitter (now known as X) networks: “This was academic DH 2010-20xx whenever Twitter died”. Others mentioned Slack, Discord, Github, Quora, Mighty and LinkedIn: “It sounds like Github meets Kaggle meets LinkedIn”. The [Canadian Humanities Social Science Commons](#) was also mentioned as an example of a trend for setting up ‘commons-like’ spaces. [IIIF](#), [Linked Art](#) and [AI4LAM](#) were also mentioned.

The general organisation of work around a network was recognised as the way in which research networks often operate, but there was also recognition that this (and the scenario) depends upon social capital and does not support work beyond a limited project lifespan. While it may be easier to build such capital in virtual spaces, without the need for travel or particular institutional affiliations, lack of social capital can ‘create barriers to entry and may exacerbate existing structural inequalities’, such as the dominance of perspectives from the Global North:

“Those of us who are well-connected in the community can get things done cheaply or for free, but I suspect that less well-connected colleagues really struggle.”

This idea was extended by another respondent: “If your culture is deemed uninteresting or small or problematic to engage with you will probably never really see it online unless some celeb-style DHer is interested.”

Concerns were also raised around not using resources to reinvent the wheel when social networks/platforms already exist (github was mentioned at this point) and proliferate. However, there was interest in the community support aspect, which was recognised as existing, but difficult to access due to the time constraints of experts: “Those of us at the coal-face are too busy making things work to spend significant time helping others out (although we want to and actually enjoy helping – constraints don’t always allow it).”

The limited lifespan of projects and funding was a recurring theme, with the lack of sustaining infrastructure leading people to take on uncompensated labour to keep things running, and the need to “beg/borrow equipment, bandwidth and power from

the organisations we work for”. This dependence on free labour and goodwill was seen as a challenge for both setting up and sustaining the infrastructure, as was the lack of investment and structured support.

There was recognition that institutions may support their own digital projects for purposes of self-promotion, while independent or external projects may be ignored or opposed. In the workshops, some participants saw the scenario as one which needed other infrastructure systems to build upon. Elsewhere the scenario was described as giving ‘cyberpunk vibes’ in its transience. Although some respondents found this uncomfortable, it was not unanimously seen as negative – the fragile and temporary nature of projects can prompt project leads to pay attention to depositing data elsewhere, and to giving projects a life beyond the involvement of their creators – described as “building it with its own obsolescence in mind”.

Magic Elves

Infrastructure is largely invisible, reliable, and uncontroversial, because services are maintained and supported by a large, well-funded and well-staffed consortium. Generally, things go smoothly and, when they don't, the ‘magic elves’ of the consortium sort it out quickly. Funding is sustained, rather than project based, through national and transnational public investment and organisational membership, based on a formula which considers the size and income of each participating institution. There are established mechanisms for larger organisations to support smaller ones through representation in infrastructure decision-making groups, partnership working, and the sharing of expertise. Support is available to non-members through open resources and the collective sharing of good practice. The consortium hosts popular apprenticeship and fellowship schemes which receive government funding. These provide training, hands-on digital cultural heritage project experience, and continuing professional development to arts and humanities scholars and GLAM professionals, with experts joining the team for fixed fellowship periods to complement the expertise of the core staff and help support projects. However, new ideas are not always welcome, which has led to a newly-formed offshoot group agitating for the consortium's most recent strategy to be overturned at the next general meeting.

This scenario was considered as both ideal and idealised, with one survey respondent describing this way of working as “the pragmatist's institutionalist dream of 30 years ago”. Respondents recognised some aspects of the scenario, but contrasted it with the reality of government and public investment as being in decline or unavailable in any sustained way. More than one respondent likened this scenario to Europeana, or a more idealised version of it. Others recognised the opposition to new ideas as an organisational issue. The structure was described as top-down by more than one respondent, and one found the idea of larger institutions supporting smaller ones

implausible. Another emphasised that the value of expertise is being undermined overall by a more corporate ('MBA') management model. Workshop participants in particular expressed concern about who the magic elves were: their anonymity was seen as disguising both power and labour, and limiting user understanding.

The plausibility of the consortium model was questioned, but several people emphasised the value of collaborative working, support for smaller organisations, the sharing of resources and fluid international working the scenario proposes. Space for novelty and innovation, and the ability to respond to change were seen as important. One respondent identified the membership model with a sliding scale as a way of limiting the dominance of larger institutional partners.

However, during the workshops, concerns were raised about its size, which respondents felt risked it being unable to make these changes, and instead becoming complacent, and a single point of failure.

Thoughts were prompted about the importance of recognising the cultural value and tangible benefits of heritage from a 'rounded perspective', in the perceived current context of little value for money and the influence of political perspectives. This was balanced by some frustration around 'established ways' of doing things without input from the bottom-up (including the input of users). Recognition that some tech workers in the sector are 'overworked and underpaid', but trying to find work that fits with their values, balanced with the view that here are 'no real specialists in cultural heritage technologies' but IT generalists who are expected to do everything:

"There is no team to look at new developments in AI or better ways to aggregate data sets, we are barely keeping our heads above water. Training is patchy, the newer skill sets are not appreciated and often poorly graded. Software development is poorly resourced and there is never any time between developments to work on core housekeeping."

Reference to the [2023 cyber-attack on the British Library](#)* was made as evidence that the development of centralised expertise and the sharing of best practice is essential. Stable funding was welcomed, particularly to lift the burden on individuals and small organisations of searching for project-based funding while promising that projects will be sustainable in the longer term. There was a warning against a model which encourages a proliferation of projects to be created which are environmentally unsustainable in terms of data storage. Another survey respondent commented that the model "seems like a utopia in the current funding landscape".

*See <https://web.archive.org/web/20240613064857/https://www.bl.uk/cyber-incident/> for update at time of writing.

SASi

Increasingly, researchers are engaging with the “Stop Asking Stupidly” (SAS) methodology as part of their process. The SASi tool was built to support this methodology. It doesn’t replace more streamlined mechanisms for exploring objects and collections, but with its flexible, AI-powered discovery functionality it helps tap into less obvious possibilities and questions. It draws on social metadata, the rich contextual information held about objects, and any available historical information about the collection and digitisation processes that have shaped what is available. It also prompts speculation on what is not represented: gaps and silences in the records, questions that have not been asked, and analysis that has been under the radar. Its purpose within the infrastructure ecosystem is to add friction. One of the more surprising aspects of its success has been the popularity of the option for SASi to be quite blunt and confrontational. Usage data shows a marked increase in the amount of aggression and challenge SASi is asked to provide. It is living up to its name.

There was disagreement about whether this scenario would be desirable, but many respondents thought it was feasible. This possibly reflects a degree of hype about AI and its capabilities, which some respondents were quick to challenge, and others found compelling. Responses to this scenario reflected a range of attitudes to AI more generally: as something to fear, as a source of possibility, and as a tool, whose functioning depends on how people use and explain it. The range of responses reflects the fact it is currently a transitory technology. However, warnings about accepting such visions of AI futures were stark, with concern about AI’s lack of clarity, environmental impact, in-built biases, and potential to undermine experts and defund cultural institutions for what will ultimately be bad outcomes:

“This is basically just DH folks getting high on Copium while calling it Hopium... A managerialist, taylorist mirage designed to desperately divert a small rivulet of funding away from the AI/fintech torrent currently pounding our local, national, and international institutions to utter irrelevance.”

For those who saw positive potential in this scenario, such potential centred on the promise of reading objects and collections differently – through a decolonial or Indigenous lens, for example, and taking a serendipitous, exploratory and questioning stance to gaps and silences. There were also comments about the potential for methods of digital engagement that were more accessible – to non-experts, and potentially to disabled people (for example using screen readers as interfaces for these kinds of interactive engagements with digital collections).

Other respondents thought such a system would have to rely on rich metadata, the continuing input of human experts, and trusted sources for AIs to draw on. This suggests that an automated system that can be provocative even where information is limited might not be desirable. This is interesting, since (as one respondent pointed out), gaps and silences are “features of the records”, and several respondents saw this as worthwhile to become more aware of. So perhaps the issue here is about what is doing that awareness-raising, and how.

Several workshop participants brought up the relationship between human and non-human participants. They framed SASi in the context of issues of empathy, cultural bias and trolling, and wondered how people might humanise this digital tool. This suggested questions about how its perceived gender, race and friendliness might influence engagement with it.

The “blunt and confrontational” option for SASi was largely dismissed by survey respondents – they criticised the idea that there could be a “stupid” question, and noted that aggression would never be a good way to present re-readings of cultural heritage, as it might “deter engagement”. However, the workshop participants were a bit more enthusiastic, engaging with it as a source of entertainment, stealth learning, and exposure therapy for people who struggle to engage with difficult histories. They did propose there being an off-switch, though, so visitors can ‘be inspired, see something beautiful, not challenged’, if they choose. One survey respondent described the scenario as “grown up” and had a positive response to it – but they highlighted that the success of such a technology would depend on discovery tools that “really understand” the data they are presenting.

Green Machine

The Green Machine infrastructure prioritises environmental sustainability throughout its design. Access is only available during certain times, so that the servers aren’t eating up energy 24/7. The interface is minimal, with no extraneous graphics – the focus is the search bar. The only other feature of note is a dial showing how much energy each search is using. This reminds researchers that there is a material cost to using digital resources, encouraging efficiency and thoughtfulness when designing searches. Storage efficiency means metadata is also limited, so researchers often work with a bank of keywords rather than bespoke searches. Those searches might take some time too, thanks to the low bandwidth – but waiting longer for results means more time for our planet. The Green Machine gives researchers access to a centralised collection database, referring them to cultural heritage collections across the network of organisations. Centralisation means information isn’t duplicated, so that minimal server space is taken up. What is returned is of good-enough quality, and committed researchers can ask organisations directly for more or better-quality scans or information, if they really need to. The experience isn’t exactly user-friendly but helps ensure there will be users in further futures.

Responses to the Green Machine were mixed. More survey respondents thought it was desirable and achievable than not, but only just. Some liked the scenario’s green, centralised, unfriendly approach, and others questioned these elements. There was no one element that every respondent seemed to agree would work.

In the workshops, several participants suggested ways in which the idea could be improved, suggesting the basic idea was positively received, even if the proposed practicalities were disliked.

Most positive comments were in response to the Green Machine's eco-friendly, sustainable approach. They understood it in terms of movements calling for sustainable practices, including degrowth, minimal computing and digital ethics work, and wider trends like slow shopping. It was clearly thought-provoking, and some workshop participants felt this would be one of its main benefits for users too, encouraging them to reflect on their environmental impact. One respondent wrote "I like the idea of reframing how we think about long-term sustainability around the somewhat radical notion – no less real for being radical – that our digital existence threatens the planet". The idea of being 'good enough', and 'doing less' had resonance too, particularly in the context of multiple platforms and prioritising high resolution digital objects. In the workshops, there was a clear interest in rethinking what can and should be digitised and made available online, in response to institutional pressures. A couple of people also hoped that by scaling things back, this approach could be more cost-effective or cheaper than current infrastructures, which would benefit cultural heritage institutions. Others suggested that the sector's preservative work included protecting the present for the future, making environmental work important to do.

However, respondents also had issues with the scenario's approach to sustainability: it omits discussion of sustainable fuels, and might not be the most sustainable way to do data management. Others felt that its environmental impact would be minimal, making it basically greenwashing: "We're not going to stop the world overheating by being a little bit more parsimonious in running database searches."

Its practicality was also questioned: it is difficult to centralise vast amounts of data, and would require a significant amount of metadata work for searches to be usable, and scaling back might affect provenance data. This could create more work and less flexibility and independence for cultural heritage institutions. Additionally, heritage information being stuck in a slow, centralised infrastructure – whilst other disciplines and the private sector continue to digitally innovate – would risk "marginalising the cultural heritage sector". Possible research areas may well be shut down too, as exploration would be limited. Users might be reluctant to use an unfriendly, old-fashioned system, compared to flashier, user-friendlier options. The infrastructure's success depends on people making a sacrifice, which isn't guaranteed.

The Green Machine's unfriendliness also raised concerns about accessibility in the survey and workshops. As respondents pointed out, users would need to be confident with the format, find the time to plan their searches, and be in the right place if limited opening times disadvantaged users from certain time zones. In the workshops, a few participants saw this as particularly affecting members of the public. This stands in contrast with the principles of accessibility held by libraries and museums. As one respondent wrote, "Saving the planet is important but solutions must not undermine the fundamental purposes of a museum". Of course, museums being able to operate relies on there being a planet, but a more balanced system might be found.

History of Buttons

Forget huge, slow, centralised infrastructure: small and portable is the name of the data game. Digitised collections are highly distributed, with ownership and care shared out amongst stakeholders. Shared infrastructure investment is primarily based on capacity to combine and package up ‘just in time’ datasets, with no query too specific. The surprise hit streaming documentary “A History of Buttons in the Northeast” involved several iterations of these portable datasets, becoming more precise as important discoveries were made. The “modesty turn” in the humanities made the importance of these specific histories more apparent, with the newest generation of digital scholars trained on principles of terroir, eccentricity and humility. Datasets are stored locally by those who requested them, and occasionally shared, swapped or openly licensed, but more often simply filed away.

International funding tends to be for initiatives which are ‘big and field-altering’ rather than small and portable, so there were few comparator projects identified for this scenario. However, aspects of the model were identified as similar to micro businesses with object specialisms; projects where funders require data deposit in repositories; the life sciences model of working with protected datasets which are not networked, and the way in which teachers share resources. One respondent emphasised that this model depends on a culture of specialists but also a wider population that is technically skilled: “a bit like a pipe dream in this area”. At the same time, issues were identified around findability of siloed datasets, creating challenges around access and reuse, and their ability to “contribute to the bigger picture”.

The approach is recognised as modest and “a retreat from the big ambitions and promises of data-driven research”, but potentially more participatory for a wider range of stakeholders. In the workshops, participants were enthusiastic about the personal and local connections small scale makes possible. Values of care and openness were seen as encouraged. One survey respondent considered this to be a ‘glocal’ approach, with others describing it as “data tapas” and a “good old cassette party” (focused on swaps). There were questions about whether there is a role for the institution here and whether this is a selfish, myopic or parochial way of working (or, more positively, granular, collaborative or organic).

Bespoke datasets risk being lost, but this was seen by one respondent as being positive, rather than the same records being over-viewed and over-published. A query was raised about whether this scenario required a linked open data infrastructure, and another respondent cautioned on the use of commercial platforms for this kind of sharing. One survey comment emphasised the importance of data transparency and a democratic infrastructure: “who runs this buttons system?”. Questions about who has oversight were also prominent during the workshops, and were linked with ownership, distribution, preservation, biases and standards. In the survey, concerns were raised about user documentation being closed source, closed classification, the potential for duplicate datasets, and questions around shared standards, FAIR data, and preservation. Portability was highlighted as being “still surprisingly hard to do”. One respondent also suggested that this approach would see typical online community characteristics come into play: The ‘generous few’, ‘lurkers’, and ‘exploiters’ (looking for monetisation opportunities based on the work of others).

Interoperability was highlighted as a major issue in both the survey and workshops: “the biggest and best-known resources in my field would have benefited from the insights of an information professional during their creation”. A lack of this is seen as a particular issue with the small scale. However, returning to commercial platforms, one respondent emphasises that they do not have respect for the content hosted. One comment highlights a similar emphasis on the local with collections held by Indigenous communities:

“...with either limited or public access to some material. You gain access by having the correct credentials as the data/material relates to you in some way. It’s not stored in the cloud, indigenous data sovereignty is respected, communities control access and partake in all steps from governance to selection/acquisition and so on.”

Issues were raised around ‘proprietary datasets’ and ‘the challenges of connecting data to tell better stories’, with a reminder that there are advantages to aggregated data sets around providing top level information and standardisation. Other concerns centred on copyright, ownership, licensing limits, changing language in relation to equality, diversity and inclusion, as well as potential loss of control. It was seen as something which might struggle to work without other infrastructures or systems in place. One suggestion was to build on-top of a Magic Elves-style system, whilst another proposed including community creators in this scenario, ‘who present accountability and take the burden of protecting the community and the resources they create and share’.

Overall Perspectives on the Scenarios

To get a sense of which scenarios were favoured, we asked participants in our in-person workshop and in the survey to provide quick judgements on the different scenarios. Although the form of the questions varied based on the mode of delivery, the resulting feedback gives an idea of general attitudes towards each the scenario. Across both the survey and the workshops, National Treasures was disliked, and seen with scepticism, whilst Magic Elves and History of Buttons were received more positively. However, no scenario was most favoured – in terms of being either seen positively or as the most desirable.

Figure 4: Survey responses to the scenarios, ordered from lowest to highest number of total votes.

Figure 5: Workshop responses to the scenarios, ordered from lowest to highest number of total votes.

Furthermore, no scenario was seen as entirely positive or negative, and respondents made good use of ‘probably’ and ‘mixed’ options. This reiterates the idea that infrastructure is seen in multiple ways by its users and makers, and that there is no single approach to or understanding of infrastructure.

All the scenarios were seen as achievable or probable, demonstrating that they align well with how the future of the digital cultural heritage infrastructure is currently perceived. It is notable that, in the workshop results, the scenarios seen as the ‘Most Probable’ consistently overlapped with the ‘Most Problematic’, suggesting negativity about the current path of the present.

Figure 6: Is the scenario achievable? Survey responses to the achievability of the scenarios, ordered from most achievable to least achievable.

Figure 7: Is the scenario desirable? Survey responses to the desirability of the scenarios, ordered from most desirable to least desirable.

Participant Comments About the Approach

Where people made comments about the speculative scenario approach, these were largely positive, with appreciation for how the scenarios fostered new thoughts, enabled creative and enjoyable engagements with important issues, and were able to draw on a wide range of experiences. One survey respondent with less expertise in the field noted that the scenarios were challenging to digest, and others considered how they might be practically implemented, and asked whether specific scenarios would be taken forward and how the conversations could continue. Workshop participants highlighted various connections between the scenarios, with some suggesting that they would like to do further work to select elements from each for further development. Other attendees noted that they thought an interesting next step in the process would be for them to design their own interpretation of an ideal infrastructure for cultural heritage, to add to the scenarios list.

An important comment, from the point of view of the project methodology, was this one:

“Much of the text in the scenarios seemed to lead the reader to particular (positive or negative) responses which, if planned for in your research design, does not seem like a great way to do research.”

This survey respondent was an academic expert in this area and had made thoughtful comments on four scenarios. Their reaction to the approach illustrates one of the key dilemmas in the current conversation: an assumption that there is widespread agreement about what constitutes positive and negative futures for digital cultural heritage infrastructure. In fact, each of the scenarios attracted a range of responses, with some more clearly seen as desirable (History of Buttons) or undesirable (National Treasures), but most of which were very mixed. Even where scenarios were seen as negative, people made an effort to find a positive spin. This indicates that the future of digital cultural heritage infrastructure could be more open than might have been assumed. This is one of the key messages from this research.

Key Findings from the Project

This part of the report highlights key findings from across all elements of the project: the interviews, scenarios, and responses. To identify and draw these out, we asked: What ideas need to be pushed further? Where are there tensions that need to be explored to make decisions about resourcing and design for infrastructure futures? Finally, we looked for possible gaps in the data – where people did not respond to particular ideas put forward in the scenarios, for example.

Leadership, Strategy, Expertise and Influence

Reviewing the range of responses, we came up against the question of where responsibility for digital infrastructure should sit. Many respondents made comments that had implications for digital strategy development, but although it was broadly agreed that strategic leadership is required, there was not complete agreement about who it should come from (for example governments, funding agencies, institutions, sector bodies). Specialist technical expertise was seen as being undervalued in strategic decision-making. Strategic digital leadership and a clear overview of digital developments in the field, was identified as a gap by a number of respondents.

The role of cultural heritage professionals was highlighted, sometimes in opposition to more corporate management approaches which were seen as necessary in the present funding landscape, but as lacking the cultural, technical and other expertise held by other professionals in the field. Several scenarios, including National Treasures and especially Pay to Play, were discussed by participants in terms of corporate moves to absorb cultural heritage into ways of thinking, planning and working that are at odds with other core values in the sector (openness, for example): this is an important aspect of the current cultural heritage landscape, and a key focus for further futures work in this area.

The matter of ‘where’ decision-making should sit was also discussed. Top-down strategies were perceived negatively, but so were systems which rely on the voluntary labour of experts and passionate individuals: such labour is unsustainable and difficult to secure. Regulations and standards, both present-day and in the scenarios (such as Buddy System and History of Buttons), bring positive benefits but limit experimentation and horizon scanning.

Participants shared many experiences and views that indicate a sense of resignation – both through acceptance that things are the way they are, and through frustration and feelings that things could be different. Frustration was particularly evident from early career participants and those who did not feel that they had direct influence on strategic decision-making, with participants highlighting a lack of influence and agency not only towards what might be desirable, but towards what is not wanted. This was seen in responses about digital infrastructure and strategy, and in terms of ways of organising that relate to structures described in Buddy System, the Old Farm and others.

Organising and Organisational Forms

Responses to organisational forms described in the scenarios tended to either recognise them as existing ways of working, often seen as undesirable, or to perceive different forms as unfeasible, even if desirable. For example, there was a lack of confidence in a networked or consortium approach in which bigger organisations could support smaller ones, or a pay-what-you-can according to size, even though these approaches were seen as potentially positive and beneficial. There were significant concerns about structures being too large (for example in Magic Elves and National Treasures), and about centralisation: risks around agenda-driven narratives, bias; stagnation and lack of direction; cultures of scrutiny and mistrust; and lack of accountability were identified. At the same time, smaller or more agile structures such as those explored in History of Buttons were also seen as risky and vulnerable. Those with experience of alternative structures such as co-operatives were optimistic about the potential for these in the GLAM sector.

Resourcing

The tendency for funding to prioritise time-limited digital projects raised one of the most significant issues that participants discussed in this research: a lack of strategic, sustainable resourcing for ambitious infrastructure developments. This linked directly to feelings of resignation about what could be possible in the future, and dismissal of the more resource-intensive models described in the scenarios – even highly centralised ones like National Treasures. A project funding model was very familiar to respondents from academia, but is also how GLAM organisations work with external funding as a driver of their strategic direction.

This is not a new situation, and we had the sense that some participants had no experience of working in any other way. The knock-on effect is that infrastructure also becomes organised on a project or funding stream basis, leading to issues around persistence, maintenance and stability. Aspects of the Magic Elves scenario and the centralisation of shared services seemed unrealistic and unachievable to participants considering this context. This made the opportunity for exploring and imagining alternatives both novel and challenging.

There was some discussion in the workshops around the cost of building AI systems such as the one described in the SASi scenario, and how expensive this kind of model would be to build, train, and operate, making it unlikely given the current business models that support AI, and the lack of funding available for this in the cultural heritage space. The Green Machine scenario also encouraged a discussion of SASi in terms of the environmental costs of AI, despite SASi's designed-in friction. Green Machine was also discussed as problematic because it might look to visitors like the institution(s) in question were unable to afford better interfaces and infrastructure.

Participants were familiar with funding being made available for initiatives similar to the National Treasures approach which made it seem more realistic as a model for the future, even if not desirable. Importantly, National Treasures describes a future where public funding exists for digital cultural heritage, albeit in a constrained form: participants noted that many challenges currently faced in the sector would be resolved through a centralised and ongoing public funding model that was sufficient to the current and future needs of digital infrastructure. As things stand, the Pay to Play scenario describes what was seen as the more likely direction of travel in both a positive sense: the sustainability of systems through membership fees, and in a more problematic one: the continued development of digital cultural heritage contingent on the extent to which it could be monetised and made into a business opportunity.

Models like The Old Farm were understood not just as feasible in their own right, but as potentially the conditions under which alternative models like History of Buttons could be subsidised and thrive (see Dependencies, below). This, and other, discussions and comments about resourcing beyond the strictly monetary led to reflections on expertise, goodwill and labour as important, and sometimes undervalued, forms of resource (as described in Buddy System, for example).

Sustainability

Survey responses and workshop discussion touched on priorities around digital preservation and the persistence of digitised material. What should be digitised, and for how long should it be kept? Buddy System, History of Buttons and Pay to Play all provoked discussion about the sustainability of infrastructure itself – including a level of discomfort that something “amazing” could happen that would not be preserved. These questions and issues have long been fundamental to the professional practices of many of our project participants, including – though differently – in relation to the collection and storage of physical materials.

However, matters of sustainability are in a process of being reframed across professions and research activities in the context of the climate crisis, particularly around digital storage and energy consumption. The energy consumption of generative AI processes was highlighted in relation to both SASi and Green Machine scenarios. SASi provoked some respondents' frustrations around

the dominance of current ‘hype’ around AI, and the risk of exacerbating unsustainable resource use through experiments that are “pouring water out the window”. The Green Machine scenario did not capture most respondents’ imaginations, reflecting perhaps a sense of hopelessness against the enormity of the climate challenge, but also seen as a retrogressive scenario for digital practitioners and in a context where digital cultural heritage is not especially high-impact, environmentally.

However, Green Machine did provoke discussion about setting a good example and showing how things could be built differently. GLAM organisations’ underlying ethos to preserve things for the future is, some thought, enabling a sensibility of responsibility to the future that could be impactful beyond the actual use of resources. Grappling with questions about not saving everything all the time (History of Buttons), and the risks and advantages of systems that can’t survive, highlighted the importance of the multiple dimensions of sustainability to discussions of infrastructure futures.

Small Data Futures

The History of Buttons scenario was popular amongst respondents, and seemed to offer a more modest option amongst the big ambitions illustrated in a number of the other scenarios. Some of the interest in this scenario was undoubtedly due to our participants forming the kind of audience for whom the idea of a history of buttons in the northeast was, in itself, an attractive topic. There was some hope that the imagined documentary on this topic might be real*. However, the process described in this scenario was also attractive: it represented a way of organising that recognises the importance of small, high quality, specific datasets to the digital humanities, in a form which is manageable, portable, and less resource-intensive than other ways of working. The potential that such a process might have beneficial impacts for knowledge, too, was raised: that it might prevent over-valuing of what is “popular”; and be better able to respond to changing narratives, possible obsolescence, or even collapse. Respondents also reflected on the risks of highly open, accessible datasets being devalued by the way they are incorporated into and monetised by big platforms, including AI platforms, and considered History of Buttons as a possible antidote to this.

The value of personal connection and local context, the ability to connect to and through communities of interest, and the privileging of depth of breadth were qualities that were highlighted as beneficial in this scenario and the futures imagined for it. Respondents also perceived positive values of openness and distributed care in this scenario. More exploration of a “small data” model and the possibilities and tensions within it would be beneficial for an understanding of data management and standards in contexts of constraint and change.

Dependencies

Though these scenarios were presented as distinct situations, participants began to suggest connections between them and point out where interconnections might fruitfully, or by necessity, exist. For example, there were negative feelings towards the Old Farm scenario, but also recognition that this form of organisation and organising might necessarily underpin and overlap with structures in other scenarios such as the Buddy System and Magic Elves. Organisational dependencies were highlighted – for example, one participant recognised Buddy System as similar to in-person local networks used to support the functioning of small heritage organisations, and noted that this kind of social network was often dependent on the structure and shared resources of the Old Farm. While this could be a very positive relationship, it was also recognised as a dependency, not a partnership, vulnerable to staff changes in the Old Farm network, and subject to its available budgets and resources.

Many participants drew links between other scenarios, either seeing their own work or projects in the sector as a combination of aspects of a couple of them, or suggesting that some scenarios as perhaps existing within the same future world: for example Green Machine and SASi may be needed to balance each other out; and History of Buttons might only work beside a well-funded

**Several months after the creation of the scenarios, we realised that our own invented documentary was, in fact, a subconscious reference to a fictional book written by the character Terence Seymour in the BBC TV series “Detectorists” – “Common Buttons of North West Essex” – see this imagined book cover from designer Sean Coleman, June 2024: <https://x.com/colemandesign/status/1807114224327426181?s=46&t=N8RmNJh-ISW4p-Tc5sat5Q>.*

infrastructure, for example Magic Elves. A workshop participant reported asking a colleague they work with on a repository project: are we Magic Elves who live on the Old Farm?

Expert networks themselves are structured around certain dependencies, often resource-driven (for example, those in well-resourced organisations can contribute more or differently to the network), and reliant on social capital. This extends beyond infrastructures like that in Buddy System, and connects to wider issues about competitive funding landscapes, and project-driven delivery of core services. There was a sense, then, that in the real world (including possible future worlds), infrastructure is networked beyond any particular platform or organisational form, with both institutional and post-institutional realities in play, and scenarios are therefore something of an artificial boundary in a complex landscape. One specific example of this was the tendency to see Europeana – an existing infrastructure that has been extremely significant in the sector over the past two decades – as embodying many qualities that appear in different scenarios. A more granular approach to the features in the scenarios might permit more flexible re-imagining of infrastructure futures in subsequent work that builds on this research.

Implications for Research and Practice

The multiplicity of views expressed by respondents indicate that the digital cultural heritage infrastructural space is far more nuanced and less predictable than previously imagined: any proposal which assumes that a simple search box on top of a unified catalogue is the solution to the provision of digital cultural heritage misunderstands both the complexities and the possibilities of this space.

However, real world concerns regarding resourcing act as constraints to imagination, in a sector which – under ongoing austerity measures in many places – has not had the luxury of designing creative digital interventions. Responses to our project scenarios emphasised various challenges in the sector surrounding leadership, resource allocation, sustainability, and organisational structures, including support, interoperability, long-term digital preservation and disaster recovery. Accessible and customisable tools, provided alongside adequate training resources, could ensure digital cultural heritage infrastructures meet evolving needs and demands across diverse audiences. However, we acknowledge that a lack of adequate resourcing sits at the heart of many of these issues, and the further provision of tools and platforms will not be possible until this funding situation improves. Nevertheless, researchers, funders and practitioners in this space must be cognisant of the potential for, as well as the many barriers to, innovation.

This project has highlighted the tension between different priorities, depending on what the purpose of digital cultural heritage infrastructures has been presumed to be, including increasing access, potential for revenue generation, environmental concerns, national promotion, prioritisation of data provision over storytelling, or the need for skills development. This research has been an exercise in uncovering these different priorities and value structures, and allowing funders, providers, and researchers to explore the frameworks they need to navigate when making difficult decisions regarding the deployment of scant resources.

Beliefs and experiences about ‘how people are’, ‘how organisations are’ and ‘what heritage is’ made a difference to how scenarios were seen. Future work might explore these beliefs and experiences in more detail, for example by adding discussions of how to make ‘good’ futures from different scenarios, and considering what future forms of heritage might need, infrastructurally.

We have shown in this project that speculative methods can open up a useful conversation space around the current context of digital cultural heritage infrastructure and its role in the management of, and access to, digital collections. The discussions that have taken place around this research have been received positively, with participants and others who have encountered it welcoming the opportunity to pause and consider what digital cultural heritage infrastructures

both offer and need. We suggest that speculative research methods can create a space for fruitful discussions in the creative and cultural industries, helping us imagine possible future interventions, while also providing a different lens to understand how we innovate from current viewpoints. The scenario texts remain publicly available for use and adaptation by others, and they may be of use in strategic planning, with a focus on reviewing current activities and aligning these with potential future directions and alternatives.

Conclusion

This research project aimed to explore infrastructural aspects of digital cultural heritage. Deploying speculative research methods, it set out to examine the decision-making involved in developing or using digital infrastructures within the GLAM sector and related fields, focusing on their long-term implications. Initial expert interviews shaped the creation of speculative scenarios that were examined through a survey and workshops. These scenarios drew on a comprehensive literature review, capturing a variety of perceptions of digital infrastructure roles and exploring underpinning assumptions about their future use.

The resulting findings aim to open up necessary conversations regarding what is being prioritised and funded to support digital cultural heritage infrastructures, and to influence further conversations and decisions around their support and resourcing. Sustainability – both structural and environmental – emerged as a recurrent theme, with short-term funding leading to short-lived projects, limiting opportunities for enduring infrastructural benefits. Significant concerns were raised about how power and knowledge are shaped by existing infrastructures, affecting what knowledge is preserved or discarded. Furthermore, interoperability and open standards were highlighted as crucial for future infrastructures to support more extensive and integrative use of digital assets.

The use of speculative design in this research proved instrumental in challenging and expanding the collective understanding and imagination of possible digital futures for infrastructure. By constructing vivid, narrative-driven scenarios, the project encouraged participants to imagine diverse and sometimes radical digital futures, interrogating current assumptions and practices. This approach not only sparked lively discussions about the preferable paths for digital cultural heritage infrastructure but also highlighted contrasts between the ideal visions and pragmatic challenges encountered by GLAM institutions. Speculative design served as a powerful tool to creatively engage with uncertainty, allowing stakeholders to begin to map out complex infrastructural needs and priorities. Overall, the responses to our scenarios showed that digital cultural heritage infrastructure has the potential to be a creative, innovative space, and that no funding council or organisation should presume to know what user groups require without undertaking in-depth consultation and design work.

In conclusion, this project underscores the necessity for a thoughtful recalibration of how digital infrastructures are envisioned, implemented, and sustained in the cultural heritage sector. By continuing to employ and refine speculative design methodologies, stakeholders can better anticipate future needs and creatively address the evolving challenges of digital cultural heritage. This not only enriches the sector's capacity for innovation but also provides the vocabulary and framework to help lobby for support for digital cultural heritage, to ensure tangible and intangible cultures are preserved, accessed, and valued across future generations.

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Research Team

Jen Ross – project lead. Jen is Professor of Digital Culture and Education Futures at the University of Edinburgh. She is co-director of the Centre for Research in Digital Education, and co-lead for the Digital Cultural Heritage cluster at Edinburgh Futures Institute, with involvement for many years in the Cultural Heritage work for the European Una Europa/Una Futura collaboration. She has been working with the cultural heritage sector for fifteen years, from the National Museums Online Learning Project in 2007–09 to the ‘Digital Footprints and Search Pathways’ project in 2021–22, and she led the 2015–16 Artcasting project (AHRC) which worked with Tate and National Galleries of Scotland to explore new approaches to evaluating engagement with the ARTIST ROOMS on Tour programme.

Philippa Sheail – project co-lead. Phil is a Lecturer in Digital Education at the University of Edinburgh, working with the Centre for Research in Digital Education and the Centre for Data, Culture and Society. She co-leads the Digital Cultural Heritage cluster along with Jen, and teaches on the MSc in Digital Education, with a focus on information literacies and research methods. Her research interests are interdisciplinary, based in higher education and digital culture, but drawing on organisational theory, science and technology studies, and social theories of time. Phil previously managed the Scottish Digital Library Consortium (SDLC), while a member of the digital library team at the University of Edinburgh. She researches digital education and academic libraries, with a particular interest in practices of organising in a research library context, and is conducting ethnographic work on crowdsourcing, digital volunteers, and public pedagogy/education.

Melissa Terras – project co-lead. Melissa is Professor of Digital Cultural Heritage at the University of Edinburgh's Design Informatics in Edinburgh College of Art. She joined the College of Arts, Humanities, and Social Sciences in October 2017, leading digital aspects of research within CAHSS at Edinburgh as Founding Director of the Centre for Data, Culture and Society (2018 -), CAHSS Digital Information Officer (2017–2022), as well as building digital capacity in the new Edinburgh Futures Institute as EFI Research Director (2018–2023). Her research focuses on the digitisation of cultural heritage, including its technologies, procedures, and impact, and how this intersects with internet technologies. She was an Alan Turing Institute Fellow 2018–2023, and serves on the Board of Directors of Transkribus.

Cate Schofield – project researcher. Cate is a Scottish Graduate School Arts & Humanities funded student undertaking a collaborative PhD in English, co-supervised by the University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh Napier, and the Edinburgh UNESCO City of Literature Trust. Her research focuses on literary heritage sites, considering how their content and experience might be made more inclusive. Cate's interests are interdisciplinary, encompassing cultural studies, heritage, tourism and museum studies, and digital humanities.

Further Information

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